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Welcome to our April 2023 newsletter

Bringing you news of past, present and future events and activities.

This issue brings you a report of the latest Data School which took place in Atlanta, USA and we are profiling two of the students together with a student who participated virtually at the Trieste, Italy summer school in July 2023.

Read about CODATA's co-located workshops at the recent RDA 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden and the work of two RDA Interest Groups, one in the field of Open and Responsible Research, the other in Research Data Management. You can also catch up on the Schools of Research Data Science (SoRDS) RDA Interest Group session at the RDA plenary and read about two upcoming data schools.

Atlanta Data School November 2022

From 7 September to 3 November 2022 an instance of the schools was run at Georgia Institute of Technology in Atlanta, USA. The school was novel in many respects. The focus of the school was on health equity. Attendees of the school were researchers

from minority-serving institutions (MSIs) in the southeast of the USA. MSIs are higher education institutions in the USA where a significant fraction of their

Tribal Colleges and Universities.

The school was run on a hybrid basis with a small fraction of face to face teaching for all the students with the majority of teaching carried out on an online basis. This school made use of the SoRDS curriculum but given the attendees research interested spotlighted biological and social health equity data. The pilot nature of the school gave the organisers opportunities to learn how to make future health-related events more engaging and valuable to the attendees. There are plans to run a similar event in Atlanta and we look forward towards future events that will serve international students studying health informatics and other data-centric disciplines.

Alumni Profile

Nii Tawiah

I am an Assistant Professor with the Department of Sociology and Criminal Justice at Delaware State University. I study disparities in access to medical treatment for substance use disorders among minoritized groups and the utilization of machine learning and artificial intelligence approaches to improve public and population health equity.

My current interests and future career goals focus on creating equitable pathways for health literacy and health equity among marginalized populations, data literacy, and data science education, bridging the data science diversity gap and integrating machine learning into social science research.

I had the opportunity to participate in the 2022 SMART-DART Program: Health Equity Cohort hosted by the South Big Data Hub in collaboration with CODATA-RDA, Microsoft, and AIM-AHEAD Southeast Hub at Morehouse School of Medicine. The SMART-DART Program was practical and rigorous. I was introduced to the software carpentry website, which provided me with refresher training in R. In addition, the instructors were available to address any questions I had.

The in-person section of the program was my favorite. I interacted with other university and organization participants, instructors, presenters, and organizers, and it also facilitated a collaborative learning environment.

This program has opened avenues for me to help build the next-generation digitized workforce, improve students' analytical ability, present students with opportunities to experience career pathways, and facilitate the application of new concepts and skills in actual work settings.

Alumni Profile

Ayishih Bellew

I am an Islander from the US Virgin Islands (USVI). I love the warm weather and being able to view the sea wherever I am. Being an islander comes with the reality that I am separated from the mainland US by miles of water. While we are called the US Virgin Islands, many of the US data sources contain little or nothing on USVI residents. There is a grave shortage of readily available data for the USVI.

I am a statistician at the University of the Virgin Islands, (UVI). At UVI we are pushing into the age of AI and ML. In 2021, I was a part of a team to create a certificate in data science for UVI students. I have taught a data management course for incumbent government workers that are managing projects and grants. I have a Masters in Data Analytics from Georgia Institute of Technology that I received in 2019.

CODATA-RDA was a fast paced data science foundational program that introduced me to tools, skills and a peer network. While I have a degree in Data Analytics, I learned a lot from the tools presented. Data science is a large field and growing. I am thankful for the opportunity to have access to the training materials. I am very interested in offering the course to my colleagues. I have been trained and now I am determined to pass on the knowledge. My hope is that UVI will be the hub for a data repository for the USVI.

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future - RDA Project

In November last year we started a new project that was funded by [EOSC Future](#), in collaboration with the RDA. This project allows us to improve the 'back-end' of running SoRDS. For this project we have employed Patricia Herterich, who normally works for Open Life Sciences to carry out the documentation aspects of the project and have just employed Thomas van Erven to carry out the IT related aspects of the projects. Patricia has been enormously busy and has implemented the following.

Formalising processes

A costing spreadsheet to host schools in high income countries has been set up and a template Memorandum of Understanding has been developed. A review

session providing new instructors with all the knowledge they require to teach at a CODATA-RDA SoRDS as well as an application process for anyone interested in joining the instructor training.

Curriculum materials

The existing curriculum material has been reviewed. All existing curriculum material on Zenodo and vimeo has been reviewed and its metadata checked against the minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources recommended by RDA. The curriculum material has furthermore been annotated using the terms4FAIRskills ontology (<https://terms4fairskills.github.io/>).

The published curriculum material has been compared with the material used to teach the latest instances of the school. Based on that analysis, a first draft of guidelines on how to update curriculum material and publish updates has been developed which will be iterated as part of the scrutiny sprint on 26 April 2023.

Platforms

A cloud instance of Moodle has been purchased which will be used as a test bed for delivering teaching. It will be used for an instance of the school being run in South Africa in May and June. For the rest of the project work will be carried out to integrate the different online aspects of SoRDS.

Patricia Herterich

Patricia is the in-house consultant to the [CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science \(SoRDS\)](#), supporting the operationalisation of running the schools. Patricia has a 10-year career in Open Science with focus on research data management and training. She holds a MA in Library and Information Science from Humboldt University of Berlin, Germany (2013) and has worked at CERN's Scientific Information Service, the University of Birmingham, and the Digital Curation Centre at the University of Edinburgh. Patricia is a Software Sustainability Institute Fellow and Open Life Science Resident Fellow with focus on developing the OLS Fellowship and consultancy capacity.

SoRDS Advisory Board Co-chair Profile

Marjan Grootveld

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Following the set up of the SoRDS Advisory Board, two co-chairs were nominated, Marjan Grootveld and Paola Gonzalez Vargas. In this issue we are profiling Marjan.

In 2019 I had the privilege to participate as an instructor in new strand of training in the CODATA-RDA Data Science Summer School: a week about data stewardship training, with a small group of aspiring data stewards. So far my research data teaching expertise drew mainly from the long-standing training [Essentials 4 Data Support](#), provided by Research Data Netherlands, and from European projects. [FAIRsFAIR](#), one of these projects, sponsored the school and the data stewardship stream. Meeting participants and some of the School's instructors in Trieste and learning more about the global mission and impact of the Schools was a great experience.

My place of work is [DANS](#) (Data Archiving and Networked Services), which is the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data. Although we are part of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), DANS is not a research institute, but rather a service provider. In addition to data repository services, we provide many data-related trainings, often with project partners, which we also see as a service. I'm very pleased that Louise Bezuidenhout, co-chair of the Schools, is our training coordinator.

My background is in computational linguistics and I have worked mainly in knowledge management and data management. In the same year I received the very flattering invitation to join the Advisory Board for the Schools (2021) I co-authored "[Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands: competences, training and education](#)", which makes recommendations to research funders and research institutes about a data steward curriculum and job profile. Although the report reflects the Dutch situation – many universities in a small, densely populated, high-income country – there may be elements in the curriculum and case studies that are of broader relevance.

Upcoming Schools of Research Data Science

This online school provides early-career African/South American researchers (M-level to postdoc) and professionals with the foundational data science skills, which include technical skills and responsible research practices, to enable them to work with their data in an effective and efficient manner required by 21st-century research.

Full details [here](#)

Summer School, Trieste, Italy 31 July - 18 August 2023

The CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School and Advanced workshops on Extreme sources of data, Internet of Things(IoT)/Big-Data Analytics, Compute Infrastructures, Data Policy, Data Documentation Initiative and Urban Data and Disaster Risk Reduction.

The call for applications will be opening soon. Visit the [host ICTP's website](#) for further details.

Alumni Profile

Martha Alade

The metaphor "standing on the shoulders of giants" meant much more to me after attending the 2022 CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School in Trieste, Italy. It was a transformative experience that would last a life time.

I am a PhD candidate in Computer Science at the Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma, Nigeria. My study focuses on the application of Machine Learning Algorithms to analyze data for Epistemological Framework; to inform Gender-Equitable driven policies in Africa. I have had bottlenecks along the way, especially in data management as well as selection of the right tools for the kind of data analysis and interactive visualization required for my project.

Attending the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School exposed me to best practices in research data management and enabled me select the right tools for my research. I was immensely inspired by the lessons on R which i now use for my Phd research. I have also improved and gained mastery of R

This experience has transformed my career immensely, accelerated my research and enhanced my skillset in Data Science and Analysis. This is priceless to me. I am thankful to the organizers and everyone who contributed to the success of the summer school.

CODATA Activities

CODATA at the RDA 20th Plenary March 2023, Gothenburg, Sweden

CODATA organised two co-located events at RDA 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, Sweden:

The WorldFAIR Project's Cross-domain Interoperability Framework Workshop

The WorldFAIR Project was delighted to welcome sixty-two highly engaged participants to the hybrid workshop, 'The WorldFAIR Project's cross-domain interoperability framework' in Göteborg on 20 March 2023.

The goal of this event was to describe the reasoning behind the development of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), to give a detailed picture of how it is currently envisioned and what activities, functions, and standards it will encompass, and to provide a current status of the work.

The EC-funded WorldFAIR project is coordinated by CODATA, with the RDA as a major partner, and will produce an initial draft of the CDIF recommendations. Building on WorldFAIR, and other expert communities, a Working Group and Advisory Group have been established to oversee the development of CDIF. It is expected that CDIF will persist beyond the scope of the initial WorldFAIR Project, and include not only the eleven domain case studies, but also other interested communities. Efforts will be made to align with major global initiatives and infrastructures addressing data interoperability (such as EOSC, ARDC, UNECE Modern Statistics).

Read [here](#) for the full details and links to recordings.

DDI Cross-domain Integration (DDI-CDI): Optimising your Data Description for Integration and Reuse

The goal of the DDI-Cross-Domain Integration ([DDI-CDI](#)) workshop on 24 March 2023 was to explain the mechanism employed by DDI-CDI and how it

recording are now available for those who would like to catch up with – or revisit – the material presented on the day. Please visit [here](#) for the slide links.

DDI-CDI is a model-based, platform- and technology-independent specification designed to supplement the metadata holdings of data disseminators, archives, and producers. By allowing for an expression of structural metadata, with references to external controlled vocabularies and ontologies, and by connecting metadata records intended for discovery, provenance, and process description, DDI-CDI can act as a connector format which is independent of domain standards. Typically, it can be produced in a programmatic fashion from existing metadata records held in more domain-specific models, although it can also be used as a stand-alone specification. It supports granular, machine-actionable description of a wide variety of data, from traditional wide data files to event/streaming data to key-value (“big”) data and multidimensional cubes.

Please visit [here](#) to read the full details of the workshop.

RDA Activities

Open and Responsible Research

[RDA for the SDGs Interest Group](#)

Ingvill Constanze Ødegaard

[The RDA for Sustainable Development Goals IG](#) aims to support advancements in managing and sharing SDG indicator data through implementation and adaptation of RDA outputs and activities.

Alignment of the SDGs with international principles of data management and research ethics remains a barrier to collecting, storing, merging, and analyzing data for monitoring SDG metrics effectively. Such principles of importance include [F.A.I.R.](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), [TRUST](#) (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology), and [CARE](#) (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics). Improving data interoperability nationally and internationally may both enhance monitoring, as well as help to enable and support progress towards achieving the SDGs.

RDA for the SDGs Plenary Highlights

Previous RDA SDG IG plenary sessions have focused on how the UN SDGs can benefit from the adoption F.A.I.R. best practices and necessary stakeholder

RDA Interest Groups and Working Groups, as well as RDA Recommendations and Outputs that could directly support SDG data infrastructure and data sharing.

The RDA SDG IG has integrated lessons learned throughout these Plenary discussions into a semantic mapping of RDA outputs, recommendations, IGs, and WGs to SDG goals, targets, and indicators. This mapping has resulted in [OntoSDG](#), consisting of a front-end UI to support documenting RDA group metadata and backend semantic knowledge-graph mapping RDA groups and outputs to their applicable SDG goals, targets, and indicators. At the [P20 plenary](#) the newest version of OntoSDG was presented as well as some preliminary results of the case statements of RDA interest and working groups with regard to their alignment with the SDGs SDGs. Furthermore, projects addressing north-south and south-south collaborations were presented.

Alignment with Council Strategy

The RDA Council outlined within the [2023 Strategic Plan section 4.3.4](#) an initiative of “Increasing awareness of, and identifying RDA’s contribution to, the SDGs, with the active participation of all RDA governance bodies”. In alignment with this strategy, the RDA SDG IG provides both a tool to support systematically evaluating the contribution of the RDA to the SDGs, as well as a group for coordinating ongoing alignment and stakeholder engagement.

- [RDA 2020-2023 Council Strategy](#)
- [RDA Community Memo - Gaining International Consensus and Input on EOSC](#)

CALL to ACTION

The RDA SDG IG requests RDA co-chairs explore [OntoSDG](#) and populate applicable information for your WG/IG aims and associated outputs, recommendations, and affiliated activities.

If you would like to join the RDA for Sustainable Development Goals IG, make sure you are a member of the RDA - join [here](#) - and then simply click on *join group* on the [IG’s page](#).

We are also looking for further co-chairs- so if you are interested please contact us!

Research Data Management
[Active Data Management Plans Interest Group](#)

The [Active Data Management Plan Interest Group](#) has a case statement which starts with the following:

The proposed activity of this group is to act as a nucleus for discussing requirements for and identifying developments needed to support active (i.e. able to evolve and be monitored) data management planning.

A standard, fully developed outside RDA, which was discussed in the early stages of ADMP, has been fully developed and will soon be reviewed in ISO and should become an ISO standard “Information Preparation to Enable Long Term Usability” (IPELTU).

IPELTU recognizes that information is created, in general, in projects. Some projects are extremely large, involving many thousands of people, some are small, even down to involving a single individual. Each project goes through many stages, some of which may last years. The some of the information may be the primary aim of the project. Much of the other information (called Additional Information in IPELTU) is created as a by-product of the project. For example building a large scientific instrument can take years and will generate designs, calibration data, finance planning, as well as the data collected. Some of this may be needed for using, or replicating, the results of the project. However much of these elements are not collected in a systematic way.

The elements of Additional Information evolve by being added to or sometimes replaced over time in each stage of the project. Inspiration has been taken from the PMBOK and the DMBOK. Cycles can be identified involving Initiating activities, Planning and Executing activities and then Closing that activities, and the activities are Controlled throughout that cycle . The following diagram illustrates a project with several phases , each phase having one or more cycles.

IPELTU provides patterns of checklists of the elements of information, especially those which are relevant to the OAIS Information Model, which should be collected at each stage in a cycle, evolving with each activity (Initiating, Planning, Executing and Closing). The areas of Additional Information which are discussed in IPELTU are as follows:

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Information, Fixity Information, Access Rights Information, Packaging Information, Descriptive Information, Packaging Information.

- From Outside the Information Model: Publications, Related Datasets, Potential areas of use of the Information etc.

Not all the information will need to be preserved, but it certainly will NOT be preserved if it is not collected. IPELTU will help ensure that these items are not forgotten.

If you would like to join the RDA Active Data Management Plans IG, make sure you are a member of the RDA - join [here](#) - and then simply click on *join group* on the [IG's page](#).

RDA 20th Plenary 21-23 March 2023

RDA Plenary meetings are the twice-annual meetings where members of the RDA community hold Working and Interest Group and Community of Practice collaborative meetings and Birds of a Feather (BoF) meetings to discuss possible new topics. The Plenary meetings serve as important milestones in the life of the work of the RDA.

The [RDA's 20th Plenary](#), a hybrid event, also marked the [RDA's 10th anniversary](#) and took place in Gothenburg, Sweden thanks to the hosts Chalmers University of Technology, the University of Gothenburg and the Swedish National Data Service, the same hosts for the RDA's 1st Plenary in March 2013.

719 people attended (489 in person, 230 online) - from over 62 countries represented across 6 continents - to participate in the Plenary's 46 breakout sessions and 7 plenary sessions. If you were unable to attend, recordings of all sessions will be available to the entire RDA community from 1st May 2023. You can also [join the post plenary webinars](#) on Thursday 20th April 2023 UTC 07:30 and 17:00, organised by the RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB), to hear about some takeaways of the breakout sessions.

Not yet a member of the [RDA](#)? Join [here](#) for free, read about the [RDA for newcomers](#) and find out where the next plenary events are taking place.

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Research Data Science (SoRDS) - IG session at RDA 20th Plenary

The [CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries Interest Group](#) held its collaborative session at the recent RDA's 20th Plenary meeting in Gothenburg, Sweden.

The CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science (SoRDS) has recently started a project to make the overall processes associated with SoRDS more efficient. The project reached its half way point during the Plenary and the session was used as an opportunity to outline what the project's goals are and what has been achieved so far. A refresh of one of the modules was also discussed with feedback from the RDA community on the value add of SoRDS.

Have you enjoyed reading the newsletter? Do you have ideas for future editions? Get involved in the Alumni WG and be part of a volunteer editorial team! Just email us at dataschools@codata.org

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